

Measuring Financial Performance Using Ratio Analysis Method: An Application on the BIST Packaging Sector

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Abstract

The primary objective of this study is to compare the financial performance of packaging sector companies listed on Borsa Istanbul (BIST) with the sector averages. Ratio analysis was employed as the primary method for assessing the financial performance of the companies. Liquidity ratios, leverage ratios, activity ratios, and profitability ratios of the selected firms were compared with the corresponding sector averages. The data used in the analysis were obtained from the balance sheets and income statements available on the Public Disclosure Platform (KAP), focusing on the year-end financial statements of 2023. The findings reveal that OZRDN stands out by delivering exceptionally high returns despite its low-risk profile—an uncommon case in financial analysis. Ratio analysis results also indicate that EMNIS and BNTAS exhibited strong financial performance. While GEDZA showed positive results in terms of liquidity and profitability, the firm appears to face difficulties in utilizing its resources efficiently. The performances of BAKAB, DURDO, KAPLM, and BARMA fluctuated, at times exceeding and at times falling below the sector average. On the other hand, SEKUR, KRPLS, and MNDTR underperformed relative to the sector average, indicating structural weaknesses. It is therefore recommended that these companies implement structural reforms urgently in order to reduce risk and achieve sustainable growth.

Keywords: BIST, Liquidity, Profitability, Ratio Analysis

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Introduction

It can be said that the packaging industry is a rapidly growing sector in Turkey. According to data released by the Istanbul Chamber of Industry (ISO), 62 packaging companies ranked among Turkey's top 1,000 industrial establishments in 2022 (Ambalaj Dünyası, 2023, p. 16). According to the Packaging Industry Association, Turkey achieved a trade surplus of 2.2 billion dollars in the packaging sector in 2023. Total exports in the sector reached approximately 6.9 billion dollars in the same year, with the top five countries for exports being the United Kingdom, Germany, Italy, Iraq, and the United States (US) (Ambalaj Dünyası, 2024, p. 14). Considering the sector report published by the Ministry of Economy of the Republic of Turkey (T.C.) in 2020 and the data from the Packaging Industry Association, it can be said that Turkey has been a country with a foreign trade surplus in the packaging sector between 2012 and 2023. If we consider that Turkey last achieved a trade surplus in 1946, the importance of sectors with trade surpluses for the national economy becomes clearer.

The use of packaging in many products, from the food sector to the white goods sector, from the textile sector to the construction sector, can be considered among the main factors in the growth of the packaging sector. In other words, it can be said that the packaging sector is one of the sectors with high demand. It is believed that this high demand triggering supply is also quite important for rational growth.

Factors contributing to the development of the sector include population growth, increases in employment rates, urbanization, and rising consumption trends (Packaging Sector Report, 2024, p. 2). As population growth can lead to increased demand, the packaging sector may experience growth due to the fact that many products, whether low or high in value added, are presented to consumers in packaging. Another factor contributing to the increase in the use of packaged products is that the rise in employment levels increases income levels, which in turn triggers consumption, and ultimately, the increase in consumption demand leads to an increase in packaging use. Increased consumer demand encourages companies to differentiate their products, which in turn increases the importance of packaging (Dođaner & Temel, 2024, p. 158). Similarly, it can be said that with increased participation in the workforce, individuals seeking to save time are using more packaged products. Companies' desire to attract consumers' attention through product packaging and their efforts to gain a competitive advantage in this way can also lead to an increase in the use of packaging (Dilber, Dilber, & Karakaya, 2012, p. 161).

In sectors such as food, it can also be said that consumers tend to choose packaged products because they are perceived as more hygienic or because the products can be stored for longer periods without spoiling. The desire of people to learn more about the production and content of the products they consume as a result of rising education rates can also be an important factor in the prominence of packaged products. The information on the packaging of the product can satisfy this desire of consumers (Erdal, 2019, p. 16). It is believed that these and similar reasons have significantly increased the importance of the packaging sector.

In this context, the aim of this study is to examine the packaging sector traded on the Istanbul Stock Exchange through ratio analysis. The data used in the analysis were obtained from company balance sheets and income statements obtained from the Public Disclosure Platform. The companies' 2023

year-end balance sheets were used as a basis. Ratio analysis, which is performed using data from the balance sheet and income statement, two of the basic financial statements, is a widely used method for measuring the financial condition of companies. A review of the literature revealed that ratio analysis of companies operating in the packaging sector has been conducted less frequently than in other sectors, which was a factor in the selection of this sector. Liquidity ratios, which indicate a company's ability to convert its assets into cash in the short term and meet its short-term obligations, leverage ratios, which show a company's ability to pay off its debts, activity ratios, which show how efficiently a company uses its assets, and profitability ratios, which show a company's ability to achieve its most fundamental goal of profitability, form the basis of ratio analysis.

Figure 1: Total Exports and Imports of Turkey's Packaging Industry

Source: (<https://ticaret.gov.tr>, 2020), compiled by the authors from reports by the Packaging Industry Association.

Figure 1 shows Turkey's packaging industry export and import data for the years 2012-2023, and it can be observed that Turkey's exports exceeded its imports in all of the relevant years shown in the figure. For Turkey, which is struggling with a chronic trade deficit, sectors that generate a trade surplus are of utmost importance, and the packaging sector can be considered one of these sectors.

Literature

Acar (2003) studied the measurability of financial performance in agricultural enterprises in his study, which utilized ratio analysis such as efficiency, profitability, debt repayment capacity, and liquidity. He pointed out that the failure of small family businesses in Turkey to keep balance sheets and income statements, which are necessary tools for measuring financial performance in the agricultural sector, is a significant obstacle to obtaining reliable and easily accessible data, which is vital for measuring financial performance. The results of his study indicate that ratio values above the sector average are important for measuring performance in the agricultural sector, targeting high performance levels, and measuring a company's competitive strength, highlighting the importance of external performance analysis.

Yılmaz (2009) examined the financial indicators of two companies operating in the automotive sector in his study based on ratio analysis. The similar and distinct characteristics of the companies were identified. The study aimed to examine the performance of Tofaş and Karsan, two companies manufacturing in Bursa, in 2007 and 2008, and concluded that the 2008 economic crisis affected Tofaş less than Karsan. However, it was observed that the 2008 crisis had a negative impact on both companies. While Tofaş mainly produces for Fiat, Karsan produces for many different brands. It was noted that this situation increased the company's risk during the crisis years. Other findings include that Tofaş has a larger production capacity than Karsan and is more successful in terms of liquidity.

Gider (2011) used ratio analysis in his study examining the period between 1998 and 2003. He examined the impact of the November 2000 and February 2001 crises on the financial performance of an organization operating in the health sector and concluded that the organization was affected by the crises but managed to recover financially in the years following the crises.

Peker and Baki (2011) compared the financial status of three insurance companies using the Grey Relational Analysis Method in their study, which utilized liquidity, leverage, and profitability ratios. They determined that liquidity ratios were an important factor affecting the company's financial performance. Accordingly, they stated that a company with good liquidity ratios may also have good financial performance.

Karadeniz, Koşan, and Kahiloğulları (2014) examined the financial performance and bankruptcy risks of four sports companies whose shares are traded on the stock exchange using ratio analysis. As a result of the analysis, they concluded that two of the companies that were unable to manage their assets effectively were at risk of bankruptcy.

Meydan, Yıldırım, and Senger (2016) examined the financial performance of food companies listed on the stock exchange using the Grey Relational Analysis Method. Within the scope of the study, financial structure, cost, profitability, and liquidity ratios were examined as ratio analysis. In their study, which aimed to create alternatives for investors in decision-making, they found that the data obtained from the classical ratio analysis aligned with the alternative they proposed.

Alper and Biçer (2017) analyzed the three-year balance sheet of a public hospital and concluded that the hospital's liquidity, accounts receivable collection period, working capital, and inventory liquidation capacity were positive.

Bora and Arslan (2017) examined the 2015 financial indicators of banks with foreign capital using the ratio analysis method. Based on indicators such as the number of branches and employees, profitability, deposits, and credit, the top three banks in the sector were Garanti Bank, Deniz Bank, and Finans Bank.

Bülüç, Özkan, and Ağırbaş (2017) examined the financial performance of public university hospitals using the ratio analysis method and concluded that the hospitals included in the study generally had difficulty meeting their short-term obligations, had slow receivables and inventory turnover rates, had excessive debt, and were unable to cover their expenses with their revenues.

Berkdemir and Altun (2018) used four years of balance sheet data to obtain 21 different financial ratios and examined the financial performance of Ziraat Sigorta A.Ş., which operates in the insurance

sector, and the insurance sector, which consists of 38 companies, using ratio analysis. They determined which company received how many points according to the scoring method. They aimed to enhance the effectiveness of ratio analysis using a new method called the scoring method.

Gümüş and Çıbık (2018) used the composite ratio analysis method in their study examining the financial performance of 25 real estate investment companies listed on the stock exchange. The Dupont method was used to evaluate the return on equity of the companies and to determine the best and worst performing companies. As a result of return on equity and other ratio analyses, they concluded that Ak Merkez GYO was the best-performing company, while NUROL GYO was the worst-performing company.

Koçak (2018) conducted a ratio analysis using data from 2011 to 2016 for private, public, and foreign-owned banks in his study comparing financial performance in the banking sector. He concluded that the years 2011-2013 were positive for all banks in terms of the efficient use of equity, operating profits, and liquidity ratios. However, he observed declines in these indicators starting from 2014.

Yılmaz and Aslan (2018) used ratio analysis in their study examining the financial performance of small, medium, and large-scale enterprises in the accommodation and food services sector. Using three years of balance sheet and income statement data, the study concluded that there were differences between enterprise scales and financial indicators.

Bilici (2019) analyzed the tourism sector between 1996 and 2016 using the TOPSIS method based on the ratio analysis averages of the relevant years. The effects of the 1999, 2000, 2001, and 2008 crises on the sector during the analysis period were also addressed in the analysis. It was determined that the sector showed positive results in terms of liquidity and financial structure. Negative results were observed in profitability ratios and activity ratios. Another result obtained from the TOPSIS analysis was that the crises did not have a negative impact on the sector. In fact, according to the TOPSIS analysis, 2001, 2011, and 1999 were the top three years in terms of performance for the sector.

Çakmak and Hayırsever Baştürk (2019) first evaluated the financial performance of the insurance sector based on ratio analysis using financial data from 2007 to 2018, and secondly examined the effect of collected premiums on economic growth. They chose to use ratio analysis to measure financial performance in their analysis. As a result of their study, they found that while liquidity ratios and asset quality were adequate in the life insurance sector, they were not adequate in the non-life insurance sector. Another finding of the study was that total premiums had a positive effect on economic growth.

Göğebakan (2019) used ratio analysis in his study examining the financial performance of five energy companies listed on the stock exchange. As a result of his analysis, it was determined that companies in the energy sector covered by the study generally had difficulty financing their short-term debts, that the maturity of debts before the collection of receivables put companies in a difficult position, and that this situation led to an increase in the use of foreign resources and a decrease in profitability.

Kızıl and Aslan (2019) examined the financial performance of Turkish Airlines Inc. and Pegasus Airlines Inc. using the ratio analysis method in their study on publicly traded airlines. As a result of

the study covering the years 2013-2017, they determined that Pegasus Airlines Inc. was in a more successful financial position.

Uzunali and Görmez (2019) used ratio analysis in their study examining the financial structure of 30 metropolitan municipalities in Turkey. Using data from 2014-2017, they found that the metropolitan municipalities of Aydın, Denizli, and Muğla stood out positively from the other municipalities analyzed.

Yenisu (2019) examined the financial performance of Adese Alışveriş Merkezleri Ticaret A.Ş. using ratio analysis in his study covering the years 2014-2016. As a result of the study, he concluded that the company needed to maintain its profitability and find a solution to its liquidity problem.

Akyüz, Yıldırım, and Akyüz (2020) used the combined ratio analysis method in their study examining the financial performance of seven companies in the paper and paper products industry listed on the stock exchange. The study, which covered the period between 2012 and 2018, used the Dupont analysis method. The results of the study revealed that Alkim ranked first and Viking ranked seventh according to the Dupont analysis method.

Keleş and Özulucan (2020) used the ratio method in their study examining the financial performance of two airline companies traded on the Istanbul Stock Exchange. They concluded that Pegasus Airlines Inc. was more successful in terms of financial performance than Turkish Airlines Inc.

Yüksel (2020) utilized the ratio analysis method to analyze the financial performance of university revolving capital enterprises in his study. While the profitability ratios of the relevant enterprises were below the desired levels, their liquidity ratios were sufficient.

Dikmen (2021) used ratio analysis in his financial performance analysis of the furniture manufacturing sector between 2009 and 2019. Among the years covered by the study, 2016 was the worst year for the sector in terms of financial performance, while 2019 was the best year for the sector in terms of financial performance.

Tanç and Erciyes Eravcu (2021) conducted a financial performance analysis using data from 2012 to 2017 for six private hospitals operating in Kayseri province, and they used the ratio analysis method in their study. The fact that they were only able to access data from six of the 11 private hospitals in Kayseri was a limiting factor in the study. In their study, which used the Spearman correlation analysis method, they examined whether there was a relationship between financial value-creating factors and financial ratios. As a result of the study, they found that the data from the six private hospitals operating in Kayseri province were close to the industry average. Another finding was that financial value-creating factors affect financial ratios.

Yoloğlu (2021) used ratio analysis to analyze the financial performance of technology companies listed on the stock exchange in his study covering the years 2016-2020. Liquidity, profitability, financial structure, and activity ratios formed the scope of the ratio analysis. The study found that despite the declines in 2020, when the effects of the Covid-19 global pandemic were felt, liquidity ratios remained at a positive level for the sector. It was determined that the sector's borrowings were generally based on short-term foreign sources, while the capital structure of companies was generally financed by equity. Another finding was that the sector's profitability increased during the pandemic.

Karamahmutoğlu (2022) used ratio analysis to examine the impact of the Covid-19 process on the financial performance of sectors. In his analysis of liquidity, activity ratios, profitability ratios, and financial structure, he found that the pandemic had a positive and significant effect on liquidity ratios. He concluded that the pandemic had a negative and significant effect on activity ratios and financial structure, but no significant effect on profitability ratios.

Temel (2022) examined how Turkish Airlines and Pegasus Airlines, which are listed on the stock exchange, were financially affected by the Covid-19 process. Using ratio analysis, the study found that both companies were negatively affected by the process in terms of activity, profitability, liquidity, and financial structure, but that Pegasus Airlines was more affected.

Babacan and Akca (2024) used ratio analysis to examine the financial performance of public hospitals operating under the Ministry of Health in Turkey, using data from 2016 to 2020. The analysis revealed that public hospitals were in good shape in terms of liquidity but had low profitability ratios.

Conceptual Framework

The current ratio is a ratio that shows a company's ability to pay its short-term debts, and it is generally accepted that a ratio of 2 is considered sufficient. The acid-test ratio is a ratio that indicates whether a company can pay its debts in the event of unexpected circumstances, and it is generally accepted that this ratio should be 1. It can be said that this ratio is calculated based on assets excluding inventories. For the cash ratio, the generally accepted level is 0.20, and it can be said that this ratio shows how much of short-term debts can be covered by liquid assets (Gündoğdu, 2022, pp. 115-116).

Table 1: Liquidity Ratio Formulas

Current Ratio	Total Current Assets / Total Short Term Liabilities
Acid – Test Ratio	Total Current Assets - Inventories - Other Current Assets / Total Short Term Liabilities
Cash Rate	Cash and Cash Equivalentents / Short Term Liabilities

Source: Gündoğdu, 2022

The financial leverage ratio shows the extent to which a company's assets are financed by external sources. A high ratio may cause the company to be considered risky, which may make it difficult for the company to obtain debt financing in the market. For developed countries, this ratio is expected to be below 50% (Altınok, Acar, Kineş, & Münyas, 2016, p. 232).

The financial debt ratio, on the other hand, shows the proportion of financial debt within the total assets held by companies. The financial debt ratio includes interest-bearing debts such as bonds, short-term bank loans, and long-term bank loans (Aksoy & Yalçiner, 2018, p. 118).

Table 2: Leverage Ratio Formulas

Financial Leverage Ratio	Total Liabilities / Total Assets
Financial Debt Ratio	Total Financial Liabilities / Total Assets

Source: Gündoğdu, 2022

The turnover ratio indicates how quickly a company converts its total assets into sales. A high ratio is considered positive (Acar, 2003, p. 28). Inventory turnover ratio indicates how quickly a company can convert its inventory into cash (Alper & Biçer, p. 340). A high inventory turnover ratio can be interpreted as a company's ability to quickly liquidate its inventory, or in other words, its ability to access liquidity at a good level.

To determine the time it takes for a company to repay its debts, the debt turnover ratio must be calculated. This ratio is determined by dividing the cost of goods sold by the average trade payables (Gündoğdu, 2022, p. 123). The higher the debt turnover ratio, the faster the company can repay its debts. The equity turnover ratio, on the other hand, is a ratio that shows how efficiently the company uses its equity, and it can be said that financial structure ratios need to be known in order to evaluate this ratio more rationally. Financial structure analyses indicate that a company with adequate equity capital and a high equity turnover ratio is considered to be using its equity capital efficiently (Bülüç, Özkan, & Ağırbaş, 2017, p. 273).

As for the receivables turnover ratio, it can be said that it shows how many times a company can collect its credit receivables resulting from its commercial activities within a one-year period (Keleş & Özulucan, 2020, p. 516). It can be said that a high ratio indicates that the company can collect its receivables more quickly. It can be said that a company's ability to collect its receivables more quickly is also important in terms of its ability to pay its debts. This situation is also considered to be quite important in managing the company's cash flow.

Table 3: Activity Ratio Formulas

Asset Turnover	Net Sales / Average Total Assets
Inventory Turnover	Cost of Goods Sold / Average Inventories
Debt Turnover	Cost of Goods Sold / Average Trade Payables
Equity Turnover Rate	Net Sales / Average Shareholders' Equity
Receivables Turnover Rate	Net Sales on Credit / Average Trade Receivables

Source: Altnok & Ünal, 2016; Gündoğdu, 2022

Active profitability shows the extent to which a company's sales are converted into profit and can be said to be a ratio used to measure the efficiency of a company's assets (Bilici, 2019, p. 184). Gross profit margin can be described as a ratio that covers all expenses and contributes to the company's net profit. It is known that it is desirable for the company's expenses on the goods it sells to remain at a

minimum level and for the gross profit margin to be at a high level (Peker & Baki, 2011, p. 11). For EBITDA margin, it can be said that it is a ratio used to measure a company's operational profitability and shows the level of “Earnings Before Interest, Depreciation, and Taxes” relative to the total revenue earned by a company. A company with a positive EBITDA value is said to be profitable, while a company with a negative EBITDA value is said to be incurring losses (Getmidas, 2023).

For net profit margin, it can be said that it is an important ratio for evaluating a company's pricing and cost levels. Again, by looking at this ratio, one can get an idea of whether the company is producing efficiently (Gider, 2011, p. 91). By looking at the return on equity ratio, it can be said that it is a ratio that shows how much of the assets contributed by the company's shareholders to the company are returned and at what level the company's equity has increased (Yılmaz & Aslan, 2018, p. 48). The ROIC ratio is another ratio that helps determine the extent to which a business has achieved efficiency as a result of its investments, or in other words, the level of performance of its investments. For it to be said that the company uses its assets efficiently, this ratio must be high (Fintables, 2021). For the earnings per share ratio, it can be said that it is one of the important indicators used to determine the profitability level of a company. A high ratio obtained by dividing the company's profit for a given year by the number of shares in the market during the same period is considered positive by investors. In other words, it is assumed that a company with high earnings per share can offer high returns to investors (Gedik Yatırım, 2024).

Table 4: Profitability Ratio Formulas

Return on Assets	$\text{Net Profit for the Period} / \text{Total Assets}$
Gross Profit Margin	$\text{Gross Sales Profit} / \text{Net Sales}$
EBITDA Margin	$(\text{EBITDA} / \text{Total Revenues}) \times 100$
Net Profit Margin	$\text{Net Profit for the Period} / \text{Net Sales}$
Return on Equity	$\text{Net Profit for the Period} / \text{Shareholders' Equity}$
ROIC	$\text{Net Operating Profit After Tax} / \text{Invested Capital}$
Profit per Share	$\text{Net Profit} / \text{Total Number of Shares}$

Source: Dikmen, 2021; Fintables, 2021; Getmidas, 2023; Gedik Yatırım, 2024

Data Set and Method

In this study, the financial statements of 11 companies operating in the packaging sector on the Istanbul Stock Exchange (BIST) at the end of 2023 were used as the data set. These data, obtained from the Public Disclosure Platform (KAP), were analyzed using the ratio analysis method, one of the financial statement analysis techniques.

The companies included in the study are shown in Table 5.

Table 5: Borsa Istanbul Packaging Sector Companies

CODE	BUSINESS NAME
BAKAB	Bak Ambalaj Sanayi ve Ticaret A.S.
BNTAS	Bantas Bandirma Ambalaj Sanayi Ticaret A.S.
DURDO	Duran Doğan Basım ve Ambalaj Sanayi A.Ş.
EMNIS	Eminiş Ambalaj Sanayi ve Ticaret A.Ş.
GEDZA	Gediz Ambalaj Sanayi ve Ticaret A.S.
KAPLM	Kaplamin Ambalaj Sanayi ve Ticaret A.Ş.
SEKUR	Sekuro Plastik Ambalaj Sanayi A.S.
KRPLS	Koroplast Temizlik Ambalaj Ürünleri Sanayi ve Dış Ticaret A.Ş.
BARMA	Barem Packaging Industry and Trade Inc.
MNDTR	Mondi Turkey Oluklu Mukavva Kağıt ve Ambalaj Sanayi A.S.
OZRDN	Özerden Ambalaj Sanayi A.Ş.

Analysis and Findings

When looking at EMNIS, BNTAS, OZRDN, and GEDZA, it can be seen that these companies have liquidity ratios above average, meaning they have a high level of liquidity. It can be said that these companies have a high ability to pay their short-term debts. However, in companies with high liquidity ratios such as EMNIS, it can be thought that capital is not being used efficiently enough, and therefore, the problem of idle funds may arise.

Table 6: Liquidity Ratios

Share Code	Cari	Liquidity	Cash
BAKAB	1,53	1,04	0,20
BNTAS	4,11	3,50	1,99
DURDO	1,30	0,81	0,04
EMNIS	7,17	3,89	0,22
GEDZA	3,86	2,69	1,01
KAPLM	0,99	0,74	0,01
SEKUR	0,83	0,53	0,04
KRPLS	1,83	1,37	0,11
BARMA	1,55	1,29	0,60
MNDTR	1,20	0,91	0,02
OZRDN	4,05	2,94	1,38
AVERAGE	2,58	1,79	0,51

When looking at KAPLM, SEKUR, and MNDTR, it can be seen that the liquidity ratios of these companies are all below average. This situation indicates that these companies do not have sufficient cash reserves and may face difficulties in paying their short-term debts.

The liquidity ratios of BARMA, BAKAB, and KRPLS are close to the average. These companies are observed to be in a balanced liquid position. Additionally, it can be said that they have sufficient short-term debt repayment capacity and no idle fund risk.

Table 7: Leverage Ratios (%)

Share Code	Financial Debt	Leverage
BAKAB	23,65	48,81
BNTAS	9,92	17,72
DURDO	15,65	40,39
EMNIS	0,28	46,95
GEDZA	4,75	23,83
KAPLM	8,58	47,43
SEKUR	29,24	70,64
KRPLS	29,55	45,44
BARMA	40,73	49,28
MNDTR	13,41	44,96
OZRDN	7,07	21,08
AVERAGE	16,6	41,5

Looking at SEKUR, it can be observed that the financial debt ratio is 29.24% and the total leverage ratio is 70.64%. It can be seen that the company has a higher ratio than the industry average in both ratios. This situation shows that the company finances itself with debt and therefore has a relatively higher risk.

The financial debt ratio of the BARMA company is 40.73%, and the total leverage ratio is 49.28%. This situation shows that this company is more dependent on financial debt compared to other companies. On the other hand, the company may be pursuing different growth plans by using the leverage resulting from its high debt situation. However, this situation may create a risky situation in terms of sustainable profit generation in the future.

KRPLS and KAPLM companies also have leverage ratios and financial debt ratios above the average. It can be said that these companies have an aggressive approach to borrowing.

BAKAB, EMNIS, DURDO, and MNDTR companies, on the other hand, have leverage ratios and financial debt ratios close to the sector average. This indicates that these companies maintain their borrowing strategies at a manageable level but are also open to external borrowing.

EMNIS has a leverage ratio of 46.95 and a low financial debt ratio of 0.28%. This indicates that the company's financing is not based on financial debt but rather on commercial borrowing.

When examining the financial debt ratios of BNTAS, GEDZA, and OZRDN, it is observed that these ratios are below 10%. On the other hand, their total leverage ratios are around 25%. This indicates that the companies primarily utilize equity and adopt a risk-averse policy by avoiding excessive borrowing.

Especially when looking at the BNTAS company, the financial debt ratio is 9.92% and the total leverage ratio is only 17.72%, which can be considered low-risk levels.

Table 8: Activity Efficiency Ratios

Share Code	Asset Turnover	Inventory Turnover	Debt Turnover	Equity Turnover Rate	Receivables Turnover Rate
BAKAB	0,87	4,81	3,64	1,85	3,47
BNTAS	1,04	5,75	35,62	1,29	5,18
DURDO	0,73	2,51	5,00	1,33	3,42
EMNIS	1,37	5,02	4,22	3,35	7,58
GEDZA	0,72	2,62	13,13	0,94	4,17
KAPLM	0,87	6,19	2,39	1,72	3,05
SEKUR	0,76	4,14	2,44	2,71	3,30
KRPLS	0,81	3,59	4,91	1,34	2,17
BARMA	0,56	4,58	14,69	0,99	2,89
MNDTR	1,09	6,20	3,69	2,02	2,92
OZRDN	1,85	5,10	7,62	2,79	8,92
AVERAGE	0,97	4,59	8,85	1,84	4,27

Table 8 shows the asset turnover ratio, inventory turnover ratio, debt turnover ratio, equity turnover ratio, and receivables turnover ratio used in the activity analysis of a business.

When examining asset turnover ratios, it is observed that OZRDN has the highest ratio at 1.85, followed by EMNIS with the second-highest ratio at 1.37. These two companies' asset turnover ratios are significantly above the industry average, indicating that they utilize their assets with much higher efficiency.

The BARMA company has an asset turnover ratio of 0.56, and the GEDZA company has a ratio of 0.72. These two companies are below the average. This indicates that assets in these companies are turning over more slowly. The other companies in the study have asset turnover ratios close to the average and present a balanced picture.

When looking at inventory turnover rates, MNDTR and KAPLM have the highest rates. MNDTR has an inventory turnover rate of 6.20, and KAPLM has a rate of 6.19. This means that these companies are able to turn over their inventory much more quickly. This situation presents a positive picture in terms of production planning and inventory management. On the other hand, DURDO and GEDZA have the lowest inventory turnover rates at 2.51 and 2.62, respectively. It can be said that these companies have not demonstrated strong performance in inventory management. Other companies are seen to be operating at rates close to the average.

The debt turnover rate indicates how many times debts to suppliers were paid during the year. BNTAS has the highest debt turnover ratio among the 11 companies, at 35.62. This indicates that the company has a strong cash position and pays its debts to suppliers within short terms during the year. On the other hand, KAPLM and SEKUR have the lowest ratios among the 11 companies, at 2.39 and 2.44, respectively. It is observed that these companies maintain longer debt repayment periods.

A high equity turnover ratio, which indicates the speed at which equity is converted into sales, signifies that company resources are being used efficiently. EMNIS and OZRDN have equity turnover ratios of 3.35 and 2.79, respectively, indicating higher equity efficiency compared to other companies. It can be said that these companies are effective in quickly converting their capital into commercial activities. GEDZA and BARMA companies appear as low-ratio companies with ratios of 0.94 and 0.99, respectively. This situation indicates that these companies do not use their capital effectively and efficiently enough.

A high accounts receivable turnover ratio, which indicates how many times a year companies collect their receivables, shows that collections are made in a shorter period of time. OZRDN and EMNIS are the companies with the highest ratios, at 8.92 and 7.58, respectively. These companies may have stronger cash flow because they collect receivables from their debtors in a shorter time. On the other hand, the KRPLS company with a receivables turnover ratio of 2.17 and the BARMA company with a ratio of 2.89 had relatively lower ratios. This means that these companies collect their receivables over a longer period and may face cash flow problems in the future.

When considering all ratios, it can be said that OZRDN and EMNIS are the most efficient and effective companies in terms of operational structure. Nearly all of these companies' activity ratios

are above the industry average. Therefore, it can be said that they are successful in terms of effective sales policies, collection processes, and capital management.

On the other hand, improvements should be made in sales and marketing as well as collection processes in BARMA, DURDO, GEDZA, and KRPLS companies. In particular, the low receivables and inventory turnover rates may lead to serious cash flow issues in the future.

When viewed overall, companies such as BNTAS, SEKUR, KAPLM, and BAKAB are performing at levels close to the industry average, demonstrating balanced performance. Although these companies are not performing at a level that provides a competitive advantage, they can be said to be in a balanced and consistent position in terms of operational efficiency.

Table 9: Profitability Ratios (%)

Share Code	Return on Assets	Gross Profit Margin	EBIT Margin	Net Profit Margin	Return on Equity	ROIC	Profit per Share
BAKAB	1,10	12,34	7,67	1,11	2,36	1,67	0,60
BNTAS	21,17	17,34	14,87	17,65	26,25	11,85	1,62
DURDO	6,52	21,73	12,65	7,74	11,86	7,10	1,34
EMNIS	37,18	20,99	11,90	23,55	90,76	25,70	13,69
GEDZA	10,52	40,01	32,79	12,71	15,32	27,63	1,84
KAPLM	-4,37	12,46	3,66	-4,55	-9,86	-0,56	-3,36
SEKUR	-2,55	13,97	10,84	-3,35	-9,11	14,65	-0,45
KRPLS	-11,73	28,32	10,38	-12,52	-19,24	2,62	-0,80
BARMA	3,73	24,53	20,36	5,82	6,64	8,42	0,50
MNDTR	-10,74	14,18	3,54	-8,59	-19,99	0,53	-0,98
OZRDN	55,08	49,90	26,22	25,81	82,88	41,06	7,27
AVERAGE	9,62	23,25	14,08	5,94	16,17	12,78	1,93

Looking at the table above, it can be seen that OZRDN has the best performance in terms of both investment efficiency and operational efficiency. In particular, it can be said that there is significant efficiency in the use of resources. Looking at EMNIS, it can be said that this company performs well in terms of return on equity. This situation is also supported by its low debt structure and strong profitability structure. In terms of investment efficiency and operational profitability, GEDZA can be said to be in a very strong position. The Net Profit Margin, Return on Equity, and Return on Assets of the MNDTR, KRPLS, and KAPLM companies are negative. When looking at earnings per share,

they are seen to be in the range of -0.98 to -3.36. In other words, most of these companies are unable to use their resources effectively, resulting in losses and a negative image in terms of market returns.

The ROIC and Net Profit Margin of BARMA, DURDO, and BNTAS are in line with the sector average. It can be said that these companies have a moderate and stable profitability structure.

BAKAB's overall profitability is below the sector average. The low Return on Equity and Return on Assets indicate that the company is not performing effectively in terms of both investments and equity utilization. Although this company's sales appear to be profitable, this situation is not reflected in the operating profit and net profit ratios.

Finally, when looking at the SEKUR company, it can be said that this company has a risky structure. It can be seen that the company has failed in both equity utilization and asset utilization. However, the ROIC ratio is noteworthy for being positive (14.65%). This may indicate that the company is generating good returns from investments financed through borrowing. However, these returns are not reflected in net profit, which is thought to be due to the high cost of debt or significant tax burdens.

Conclusions and Recommendations

In this study, the liquidity ratios, leverage ratios, operating efficiency ratios, and profitability ratios of 11 companies in the packaging sector listed on the Istanbul Stock Exchange were analyzed in comparison with sector averages based on their 2023 financial statements.

The analysis results can be summarized as follows.

OZRDN has demonstrated a stable performance well above the sector average in all ratios, particularly in terms of profitability, operating efficiency, and liquidity. With its Return on Assets (55.08%) and ROIC (41.06%) ratios, it is the company with the highest investment efficiency and operational efficiency. On the other hand, the company's low debt ratios reveal a balance between high returns and a low risk profile that is not often seen.

EMNIS demonstrates extremely good performance with high equity profitability (90.76%) and strong operational efficiency. It has a strong structure in terms of collection success, effective sales management, and self-financing with almost no financial debt.

The BNTAS company has a balanced and optimal profile in terms of risk-profitability-liquidity, with strong profitability and low debt ratios. It outperforms the industry average, particularly in terms of ROE (26.25%) and net profit margin (17.65%).

The GEDZA company demonstrates strong performance in terms of liquidity and profitability, but it should pursue more effective and efficiency-enhancing policies in terms of resource utilization. Focusing on shortening collection periods will be more beneficial for this company in the future.

Companies such as BARMA, DURDO, BAKAB, and KAPLM present a mixed picture, with some ratios below average and others above average. These companies should increase the efficiency of asset utilization, optimize capital costs, and strengthen operational efficiency.

SEKUR's profitability and liquidity ratios are negative. However, the high total leverage ratio of 70% indicates that the company is at a significant risk of financial fragility. It is recommended that measures be taken regarding debt and cash management.

In MNDTR and KRPLS companies, profitability ratios are negative. Inventory and receivables turnover rates are low, while return on equity is significantly weak. These companies have structural problems in that their resources are not used efficiently and their return on equity is negative, and measures should be taken to address these issues.

This study reveals that the sustainability of business performance is not solely dependent on high profitability; strong liquidity, manageable risk positions, and efficient use of resources are also important. The strengths and weaknesses or areas for improvement of businesses can serve as extremely important references for their long-term planning.

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